

An Implementation and it's Evaluation of Password Cracking Tools Fcrackzip and Crunch

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Abstract : Fcrackzip is a password cracker written in assembler in part. It can break password-protected zip files using brute force or dictionary-based attacks, and it can optionally verify the results with unzip. Fcrackzip looks for encrypted messages in each zip file and attempts to guess the password. All files must be password-encrypted, and the more files you have, the better. Have you ever typed a password for unzip incorrectly? Unzip immediately responded with an automated message about an incorrect password instead than decrypting the entire file. But while zip's encryption algorithm is highly acceptable, PK made cracking simple with including hooks in the zip file for very efficient password-checking. Crunch is a programme which thus generates a set of words. In Kali Linux, it's a password attack tool. Dictionary Attack is the most specific use. You might choose a standard character set, a number, or symbols here. It is responsible for generating all possible permutations and combinations.

Keywords – Kali Linux, Vulnerabilities, ZIP, Crunch, Fcrackzip, Bruteforce, Dictionary Attack.

I. INTRODUCTION

Fcrackzip : It's a fast password cracker written partially in assembler. It can break password-protected zip files using brute force or dictionary-based attacks, and it can optionally verify the results with unzip. Fcrackzip looks for encryption keys in each zip file and intends to guess the password. All files must be password-encrypted, and the more files you have, the better. Have you ever typed a password for unzip erroneously? Unzip immediately responded with an error message about with an incorrect password rather than decrypting the entire file. Though zip's encryption algorithm is satisfactory, PK made cracking simple while including hooks in the zip file for very efficient password-checking.

Crunch : It's a solution for developing wordlists that comes pre-installed with Kali Linux. It's used to make custom keywords using wordlists. It develops a wordlist that can be permuted and combined. To make a wordlist, we might use some basic patterns and symbols. Brute force password attacks depend heavily on wordlists. A brute force password attack is when an attacker uses a script to repeatedly attempt to log into an account before they get a positive result. Brute force attacks are patently clear, and they can succeed in a properly configured server locking out an attacker or their IP. This is why it's

important to check the security of log-in systems in this manner. Attackers who attempt these attacks should be barred from your server, and the increased traffic should be recorded. Kali Linux includes a handy tool for making wordlists of any length. Crunch is a straightforward command-line utility. It has a basic syntax and can be easily customized to suit your specifications. That being said, be aware that all these lists can expand very large and easily fill an entire hard drive.

It was only reasonable to combine these two resources into one. It provides a standard command-line options, speeds things up a little by using a single framework case, handles all possible output formats, and makes payload generation a little more sane. The information presented in this article is only to be used in the proper manner and is not meant to lead to one being a hacker. The methods mentioned are needed to encourage one in monitoring performance related to penetration testing of one's own system or a system for which you have permission. This can only be used for educational purposes.

'Fcrackzip' - Abbreviations

- Wordlist - A dictionary file used only to fit all of the words in the dictionary with the password-protected zip file.
- Hash- fcrackzip has been used to find the password's hash value. Exploit – Running malicious code to take advantage of the vulnerabilities.
- Metadata – The password-protected file's hash value is preserved in the zip file's metadata.
- Rate of Process - The time it will take to find a password depends on the wordlist if a dictionary attack is used, and the password length if a brute force attack is used.

In this problem concept, we use the fcrackzip command to determine the hash value of the password of a password-protected zip file, which will then be comparable to a dictionary file or used in a bruteforce attack on password combinations. When using the Fcrackzip console, some important commands include:

- help (which brings up some of the basic commands).

- back (this will allow you to go back to the fcrackzip>).
- info (this will get info about a specific exploit to see where or not you want to use it).
- show (this will let you see all the available details for that specific file)

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Umesh Timalsina et al [1], is a computer security project that assists in penetration testing and IDS signature creation by providing information about device vulnerabilities. A short overview of the Fcrackzip project and Framework, along with its past. An introduction to the types of interfaces offered by the system in Kali-Linux, as well as a run-through of the Fcrackzip Framework's basic terminologies. Finally, include a few explanations of vulnerabilities on multiple platforms. The Fcrackzip project, used mainly in bruteforce and dictionary attack. The

operating systems that make use of virtualization technologies, and provide a few final remarks about the Fcrackzip Framework.

Michael D. Moore et al [2], it tells about the penetration testing in general, as well as how to use Fcrackzip . Fcrackzip is a weak system, and using any other system to do this will be considered hacking, with obviously disastrous results. We will find the bugs that need to be patched in order to better secure the device by using Fcrackzip to test a file. Certain topics, such as network protocols, firewalls, and basic security issues, will be investigated in this study, and this tool will play an important role.

P. D. Meshram and colleagues [3] a summary- The number of malicious mobile apps targeting Android-based smartphones is increasingly increasing. Furthermore, these malicious apps are capable of downloading modules from servers controlled by malicious users, resulting in the activation of unusual events inside smartphones. As a result, an attacker can use the fcrackzip tool to gain illegal access to personal information and data stored on a smartphone by gaining access with other tools and compromising the phone's passwords using either a Brute force attack or a Dictionary attack.

Himanshu Shewale et al [4] examine the Android architecture, as well as the threats and security flaws that exist. To mitigate known vulnerabilities, identify various vulnerability mitigation techniques. A thorough analysis will enable us to recognise the current loopholes and it will provide strategic direction to make android operating system more stable. The Linux kernel underpins the Android operating system. It is the most commonly used and common mobile operating system. Because of its programmable and transparent design, attackers are enticed to take advantage of it. Developers can freely

access and change source code on the Android platform. However, it also raises the risk of a security breach.

Android has the largest market share of all Smartphone operating systems, according to Tiwari Mohini et al [5]. One of the primary concerns of today's Smartphone users is security. Smartphones have become more vulnerable to virus and malware attacks as their power and features have grown. Android could be more stable than any other smartphone operating system available today. The lack of developer limitations on Android raises the security risk for end users. In this article, we looked at application-level protection as well as security problems with a zip file's less stable password.

Wei Chen et al [6] are working on ways to evade common antivirus (AV) products, as well as ways to integrate this information into Fcrackzip such that the wider security community may predict and mitigate these techniques. The culmination of this research has resulted in the introduction of Fcrackzip Framework's first-ever "evasion module." Framework users can now create evasive payloads without having to instal any external tools thanks to the latest evasion module form. It also gives developers the tools they need to create their own evasive modules based on password cracking analysis. The engineering work that underpins the Fcrackzips Framework is detailed in this paper.

III. PROBLEM DEFINITION

Using the Fcrackzip and Crunch tools, find the password of a password-protected zip file. Crunch is a tool that can be used to generate a word list for password cracking as well as a dictionary attack. We will find the hash value of the password of a password-protected zip file using the Fcrackzip tool, and it will be matched with the password string provided by the user using either a brute force attack or a dictionary attack. I'll show you how to use the Crunch and Fcrackzip software to find the password of a zip file.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

1) Wordlist Generation

To get started, open up a terminal. Crunch is already installed and ready to go on Kali, so you can just run it. For the first list, start with something small, like the one below.


```
kali@kali:~$ crunch
crunch version 3.6

Crunch can create a wordlist based on criteria you specify. The output from crunch can be sent to the screen, file, or to another program.

Usage: crunch <min> <max> [options]
where min and max are numbers

Please refer to the man page for instructions and examples on how to use crunch.
kali@kali:~$
```

Fig. 1. Opening Crunch in Terminal

Crunch <min> <max> [options]

- Where min and max are numbers.
- Options denote the character set, output, etc.

Example:

kali@kali :~\$ **crunch 10 10 -t stella% % % %**

In here, we are generating a wordlist of 10000 words.

- 10 : It denotes the Min and Max length of the words.
- -t : It denotes that we are using the following characters a to z.
- stella% % % % : It denotes that the wordlist starting with stella and ends with 4 random characters.
- -o : Output is to be stored in a file.
- dictfile.txt : The output is stored in this file.

2) Installing fcrackzip

Fig. 2. Installing Crunch via Terminal

Using the fcrackzip tool we have collected the hash of the password of the protected zip file and it is stored in the zip1.hash file. The hash can be MD5, SHA2, RC4/AES 32/64.

In this paper, we will find the hash and it is used for matching with the passwords from the dictionary file or using brute force attack.

After the purpose, test the zip file with the password generated using the tool to open the zip file.

V. METHOD OF IMPLEMENTATION

1) Brute Force Method

- It entails an attacker submitting a large number of passwords or passphrases in the hopes of correctly guessing a combination.
- The intruder goes through all possible passwords and passphrases in order to find the right one.
- We can match the hash value created with various random passwords or passphrases.
- It will scan for all possible character combinations.
- When the file's password is too long, it takes too long to open.

fcrackzip -b -c 'a1' -l 6-10 -v -u /root/Desktop/sssss.zip

Fig. 3. Finding zip password using fcrackzip -bruteforce mode

- -b : It shows that it uses Brute Force method.
- -c : It describes the character set used [here : a - z and 0 - 9] .
- -l : It denotes the minimum and maximum length of the password [here : 6 to 10]
- -v : It uses Verbose Mode.
- -u : Use unzip and path of password protected file.
- /root/Desktop/sssss.zip : It is the password protected zip file.

2) Dictionary Attack

- In this mode, we have lists of popular passwords that can be used to guess a password.
- A dictionary file is primarily a text file that contains a list of passwords.
- We'll compare the hash created from the zip file to all of the passwords in the dictionary file.
- If it fits, the password will be displayed; otherwise, Not Found will be displayed.

fcrackzip -D -p rockyou.txt file.zip

Fig. 3. Finding zip password using fcrackzip -dictionary mode

In here, the dictionary file rockyou.txt is used as a dictionary file and Fcrackzip will take each and every word from the file and take its hash value and try matching with the hash value of password protected file is stored. If any match found, then it will display the password. Here the password is **ignite**.

3) Benchmark Method

By measuring a benchmark score, we will determine which method of fcrackzip is more effective in your machine.

fcrackzip -B

Fig. 3. Finding zip details using fcrackzip -benchmark mode

- -b: for using brute force algorithms.
- -D: for using a dictionary.
- -B: execute a small benchmark.
- -c: use characters from charset.
- -h: show the help message.
- -version: show the version of this program.
- -V: validate or check the algorithm.
- -v: for verbose mode.
- -p: for using a string as a password.
- -l: for providing a specific length to password.
- -u: for weed out wrong passwords.
- -m: to specify the method number

VI. RESULT

As a result, with this three problem concept the passwords of the zip can be easily find using this tools. So we need it to secure the password of the zip file with a high secrecy.

By this result every users beware of this kind of attacks on files and also devices with password and in any operating systems, it is possible to attack. So the users have to follow some of the preventions mentioned here:

PREVENTIONS

- Don't use small passwords.
- Don't use only letters for passwords.
- Don't show the password to anyone while you opening your file.
- Don't allow downloading any apps from cloud websites.
- Don't install apps with unknown resources enabled option.
- Use antivirus in a mobile device to keep an eye on every moment of mobile.
- Always confirm with source pertaining to file to double sure
- Use numbers, alphabets and symbols for password.

VII. CONCLUSION

Finally, the Fcrackzip system is a versatile tool for gaining access to password-protected files and remote target machines. The ever-increasing need for patching vulnerabilities in the device or files can be dealt with a great deal of knowledge about them and the possibility of an attack occurring by exploiting a specific vulnerability, with more than 900 attacks obtained by various combinations of tools from the fcrackzip framework and exploit forms.

The idea discussed in this paper defeats Hash detection and other methods of determining the file's password. This framework allows you to hack any password-protected files and password-protected operating systems such as Windows, Mac OS X, and Linux, as well as build web payloads such as php, asp, jsp, and battle. In the same way, it generates script payloads such as python, bash, pearl, and others.

This attack can also be carried out on the public network using a public IP address and a port forwarding router.

One of the most important things to note is that devices connected to the same LAN can be compromised. Malware designed to circumvent anti-virus detection will continue to evolve, as will anti-virus detection techniques. Fcrackzip's evasion module was created with the goal of avoiding detection by common anti-virus software.

VIII. FUTURE WORK

Now basically the injection is manual because this Hash are stored in the metadata of the password protected zip file. The automated detection of zip file hashes will be found in the future. Then, using online mirror websites and phishing links, it's simple to target the computers or files automatically. Since it is automated, this version is much easier to use. When you download Fcrackzip Framework, it includes this option, which allows you to hack files in your browser using your device as the local host. The Fcrackzip group was created to bridge the gap between daily penetration testers and people who want to do the research but don't know anything about it.

IX. REFERENCES

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